

Review article

Neuropsychiatric symptoms in spinocerebellar ataxias and Friedreich ataxia

Simona Karamazovova^a, Veronika Matuskova^a, Zahinoor Ismail^{b,c}, Martin Vyhnalek^{a,*}^a Center of Hereditary Ataxias, Department of Neurology, 2nd Faculty of Medicine and Motol University Hospital, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic^b Hotchkiss Brain Institute and O'Brien Institute of Public Health, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada^c Departments of Psychiatry, Clinical Neurosciences, and Community Health Sciences, Cumming School of Medicine, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Spinocerebellar ataxia
 Friedreich ataxia
 Neuropsychiatric symptoms
 Depression
 Anxiety
 Apathy
 Agitation
 Psychosis

ABSTRACT

Apart from its role in motor coordination, the importance of the cerebellum in cognitive and affective processes has been recognized in the past few decades. Spinocerebellar ataxias (SCA) and Friedreich ataxia (FRDA) are rare neurodegenerative diseases of the cerebellum presenting mainly with a progressive loss of gait and limb coordination, dysarthria, and other motor disturbances, but also a range of cognitive and neuropsychiatric symptoms. This narrative review summarizes the current knowledge on neuropsychiatric impairment in SCA and FRDA. We discuss the prevalence, clinical features and treatment approaches in the most commonly reported domains of depression, anxiety, apathy, agitation and impulse dyscontrol, and psychosis. Since these symptoms have a considerable impact on patients' quality of life, we argue that further research is mandated to improve the detection and treatment options of neuropsychiatric co-morbidities in ataxia patients.

1. Introduction

Hereditary ataxias are a heterogeneous group of rare neurodegenerative disorders affecting the cerebellum and its connections as well as other structures of the nervous system such as the spinal cord, brainstem, and basal ganglia. They can be subdivided by mode of inheritance, the most common among them being the autosomal dominant spinocerebellar ataxias (SCA) and the autosomal recessive Friedreich ataxia (FRDA) (Jayadev and Bird, 2013).

SCA comprise more than 40 distinct subtypes with the most frequent (SCA1, SCA2, SCA3, SCA6, SCA7, and SCA17) being caused by CAG repeat expansion mutations. The main neuropathological hallmark is the degeneration of Purkinje neurons with consecutive cerebellar atrophy; the involvement of other nervous system regions varies among particular subtypes. The global prevalence of SCA is around 2.7 in 100,000 with a marked geographical variability (Ruano et al., 2014). Clinically, these disorders are characterized by progressive loss of gait and limb coordination, dysarthria, and often also pyramidal and extrapyramidal signs, oculomotor abnormalities, and other non-ataxia symptoms (Klockgether et al., 2019).

FRDA is one of the most common types of hereditary ataxia, with a prevalence of approximately 1–2 in 50,000. It is caused by homozygous GAA repeat mutation in the frataxin (FXN) gene. It affects mainly the

dentate nuclei of the cerebellum, spinocerebellar tracts, dorsal root ganglia, and the posterior columns of the spinal cord. At the same time, the Purkinje neurons in the cerebellar cortex are relatively spared. The major clinical features include progressive ataxia, dysarthria, scoliosis, cardiomyopathy, diabetes mellitus, and foot deformity (Cook and Giunti, 2017; Delatycki and Bidichandani, 2019).

Traditionally, the cerebellum has been linked to motor coordination and balance, however, in the past few decades its involvement in higher cerebral functions has been increasingly recognized. It is hypothesized that the cerebellum coordinates these functions in a way similar to its role in the organization of motor functions and that the disruption of these processes leads to "dysmetria of thought", analogous to the motor dysmetria (Schmahmann, 1998a, 1998b). The proposed neuroanatomic and functional base for this impairment is the disruption of the connections between the cerebellum and the cerebral cortex. The resulting set of symptoms, the so-called cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome (CCAS), includes cognitive impairment (mainly in executive functions, visuospatial function, and language) but also changes in affect and personality (Argyropoulos et al., 2020; Schmahmann, 1998a, 1998b; Villanueva, 2012). The neuropsychiatric component of the CCAS encompasses symptoms like depression, anxiety, disinhibition, irritability, apathy, obsessive behaviors, or psychotic traits. It has been observed in cases of cerebellar damage of diverse etiology (Schmahmann et al.,

* Correspondence to: Department of Neurology, Charles University, 2nd Faculty of Medicine, and Motol University Hospital, V Úvalu 84, 150 06 Prague, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: martin.vyhnalek@fnmotol.cz (M. Vyhnalek).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2023.105205>

Received 7 September 2022; Received in revised form 14 April 2023; Accepted 29 April 2023

Available online 1 May 2023

0149-7634/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2007).

A range of neuropsychiatric symptoms (NPS) has also been noted in patients with hereditary ataxia where it can arise from the degeneration of cerebellar components, although other structures involved in these disorders like the basal ganglia can also contribute (Liszewski et al., 2004).

Though less thoroughly and systematically studied than the cognitive aspects of CCAS, NPS are increasingly being examined in both SCA and FRDA. The rising interest is highly justified since NPS substantially decrease ataxia patients' quality of life (Schmahmann et al., 2021; Schmitz-Hübisch et al., 2010). Detecting psychopathology in these patients is thus of major importance as a prerequisite for effective management strategies to improve their well-being. However, despite the growing literature, a review focused on NPS in ataxia is still lacking.

Highlighting their clinical significance, this narrative review aims to summarize the current knowledge on NPS in SCA and FRDA. We aimed to examine the most frequently reported symptoms and their possible underlying mechanisms, treatment options, and the differences between the particular subtypes of hereditary ataxia, and point out the limitations of existing studies and possible directions for future research.

2. Methods

Studies covering NPS in FRDA and SCA included in this review were retrieved from PubMed, Google Scholar, and Web of Science using at least one of the following keywords: "spinocerebellar ataxia" or "Friedreich ataxia" in combination with at least one of the following keywords: "neuropsychiatric symptoms", "depression", "anxiety" or "psychosis". Further papers were identified by cross-referencing. We included studies in English published from 2000 to March 2023. Studies with any type of NPS measurement (i.e., NPS questionnaires, clinical interview, structured DSM interview, or retrospective review of medical records) were included. Only studies with autosomal dominant SCA and FRDA were included. We did not include studies focused on metabolic or other mitochondrial diseases manifesting with ataxia or studies with animal models. Methodologically, we utilized the Scale for the Assessment of Narrative Review Articles (SANRA), which incorporates key criteria such as statement of specific aims, justification of an article's importance, referencing, and scientific reasoning, to promote high-quality narrative reviews (Baethge et al., 2019).

While we are aware of the classification proposed by Schmahmann (Schmahmann et al., 2007), dividing the affective component of the CCAS into five domains (disorders of attentional control, emotional control, and social skill set, autism spectrum disorders, and psychosis spectrum disorders), we decided to categorize our results based on the most commonly reported specific symptoms, i.e. depression, anxiety, apathy, agitation and impulse dyscontrol, and psychosis, since the existing original articles lend themselves well to this categorization.

3. Results

We identified 44 studies on SCA and 18 studies on FRDA (not including case studies). Most of them evaluated NPS jointly with cognitive functions, usually with an emphasis on the latter. The majority of studies (43/44 in SCA and 18/18 in FRDA) examined depressive symptoms. 26/44 studies in SCA and 6/18 in FRDA evaluated anxiety. Other domains (apathy, agitation and psychosis) were examined in 15/44 studies in SCA and 3/18 in FRDA.

Concerning SCA, 8 studies examined genetically mixed population, the remaining studies analyzed genetic subtypes separately. Among them, 10 studies analyzed NPS in SCA1, 11 in SCA2, 21 in SCA3, 7 in SCA6, 3 in SCA17. Few studies analyzed other subtypes (SCA8, 10, 12, 14, 36).

A detailed overview of all NPS studies including their methodology is presented in Table 1 (SCA) and Table 2 (FRDA). Table 3 summarizes characteristic findings in the most common SCA subtypes and in FRDA.

3.1. Depression

Depression is the most common and widely studied neuropsychiatric manifestation in patients with hereditary ataxia.

The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) defines clear, albeit relatively strict criteria for the diagnosis of major depressive disorder (Malhi and Mann, 2018). However, even sub-threshold depressive symptoms have been reported to diminish the quality of life of patients with a neurodegenerative disorder (Reiff et al., 2011). Furthermore, some of the symptoms postulated by the DSM-5 criteria, like reduction of physical movement or fatigue, overlap with symptoms of hereditary ataxia, which can pose an additional challenge in the diagnosis. Indeed, neurovegetative symptoms of depression can be difficult to distinguish from symptoms related to other neurodegenerative diseases as well. Further clouding the issue is the fact that DSM criteria stipulate that depressive symptoms cannot be better accounted for by another medical condition, which may be the case with SCA and FRDA. Nonetheless, whether DSM criteria apply or not, depressive symptoms are debilitating and worth assessing and addressing (Ismail et al., 2018).

Most authors apply rating scales for the assessment of depression in SCA and FRDA. The most frequently used instruments are the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D), Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9), and Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS). Currently, no specific rating scale is recommended for screening depressive symptoms in ataxia patients.

In SCA, given the aforementioned ambiguity in definition and methods as well as differences between populations and subtypes, the estimated prevalence of depressive symptoms varies widely, ranging from 7.7% to 75% (Klinke et al., 2010; Schmitz-Hübisch et al., 2011), most often fluctuating between 40% and 60% (D'Agata et al., 2011; Klinke et al., 2010; Lin et al., 2018; Liszewski et al., 2004; Mastamannavar et al., 2020; Moro et al., 2017; Silva et al., 2015; Torrens et al., 2008; Yuan et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the two most robust studies with the largest cohorts of SCA patients report only a prevalence of around 17–26% for clinically relevant criteria as measured by the PHQ-9 (Lo et al., 2016; Schmitz-Hübisch et al., 2011).

Among the most common SCA subtypes, SCA3 appears to be the most affected in terms of both prevalence and severity of depressive symptoms (Lo et al., 2016; Mastamannavar et al., 2020; McMurray et al., 2006), with significantly higher rates of suicidal ideation (65% as opposed to 52% in SCA overall according to a study on 300 SCA patients (Lo et al., 2016)). It is hypothesized that this distinction can be attributed to dysfunction in frontal-subcortical circuits in the basal ganglia, which are involved in SCA3 but not in other subtypes of SCA (McMurray et al., 2006). However, there is no clear consensus in this regard as another study found a more pronounced depressed mood in SCA1 and particularly SCA6 compared to SCA2 and SCA3, even though SCA6 is considered pure cerebellar ataxia with little to no extracerebellar involvement (Klinke et al., 2010).

Data on depressive symptoms in FRDA are even more contradictory. While some authors observed significantly higher scores on depression scales in FRDA patients compared to healthy individuals (Corben et al., 2011a, 2011b; da Silva et al., 2013a, 2013b; Nieto et al., 2018), others report no significant difference in depressive symptoms (Costabile et al., 2018; Dogan et al., 2016; White et al., 2000). Among the studies that found a higher frequency of depressive symptoms in FRDA patients, the prevalence ranges from 40% to 51%, and the severity is predominantly in the "mild" range (Nieto et al., 2018; Pérez-Flores et al., 2020). One study states that 36% of FRDA patients fulfilled the criteria of major depression (da Silva et al., 2013a, 2013b). Some of the differences might be explained by a small number of patients and lesser disease severity in some studies (Costabile et al., 2018; Mantovan et al., 2006) as well as the use of only clinical diagnostic criteria of FRDA (without molecular diagnostic verification) in another study (White et al., 2000) which might result in misdiagnosis in some cases.

Table 1
Chronological summary of studies of NPS in SCA.

Title	Methods	Patients	Severity of ataxia	Depression	Anxiety	Apathy	Agitation	Psychosis	Prevalence of NPS
(Leroi et al., 2002)	DSM-IV, HAM-A, HAM-D, Y-BOCS, YMRS, assessment of apathy and irritability ¹	SCA1 (n = 2), SCA2 (n = 1), SCA3 (n = 2), SCA6 (n = 2), SCA7 (n = 1), SCA8 (n = 1), ILOCA (n = 6), sporadic cerebellar ataxia (n = 11), MSA-C (n = 5) ²	ICARS 40.6 ± 19.2	+	+	+	+	+	overall 77%, personality change 25.8% depression 67.7% anxiety 13% psychosis 10.5%
(Zawacki et al., 2002)	BDI, STAI, 4 caregivers completed the FrSBe	SCA3 (n = 6)	stage 3 (i.e., significant symptoms, patient using walls and furniture to walk) to stage 5 (i.e., confined to a wheelchair, patient can perform some activities of daily living) of Ataxia Severity Scale	+	+	+	0	NA	depression 66% (4/6), anxiety 66% (4/6)
(Rolfs et al., 2003)	standardized neurological and psychiatric examination	SCA17 (n = 15)	NA	+	+	0	+	+	47% overall
(Kawai et al., 2004) (Liszewski et al., 2004)	HADS retrospective review of neurological records	SCA3 (n = 16) 133 patients, SCA or cerebellar ataxia in 75%, MSA in 15%, an unspecified gait or movement disorder in 10%	NA NA	+	+	NA 0	NA +	NA +	NA 41% overall, depression 23%, personality change 17%, anxiety 10%, psychosis 9%, isolated hallucinations 5%, bipolar disorder 2% ³ 75% overall
(Lasek et al., 2006)	DSM-IV, GAF, collateral information from caregivers was collected	SCA17 (n = 12)	ICARS 35.17 ± 24,71	0	+	+	+	0	75% overall
(McMurtray et al., 2006)	clinical interview (for depressed mood, anhedonia and lack of interest in usual activities)	SCA 1 (n = 12) SCA2 (n = 22) SCA3 (n = 20) SCA6 (n = 22)	NA NA NA NA	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	depression 25% depression 23% depression 60% depression 27%
(Cecchin et al., 2006)	BDI	SCA3 (n = 79)	NA	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	depression 33.5%
(Torrens et al., 2008)	DSM-IV, HADS	SCA8 (n = 13)	NA	+	+	NA	+	0	9 patients fulfilled the criteria for the current psychiatric disorder (in 7/9 anxiety or phobic disorders), 6 for past disorder NA
(Suenaga et al., 2008)	HADS	SCA6 (n = 18)	ICARS 36.4 ± 12.0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Saute et al., 2010)	BDI	SCA3 (n = 49)	SARA 14.5 ± 7.5	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	depression 63.3%, moderate or severe depression 34.6%
(Klinke et al., 2010)	BDI	SCA1 (n = 8) SCA2 (n = 3) SCA3 (n = 15) SCA6 (n = 8)	SARA 12.5 ± 4.7 SARA 3.8 ± 1.4 SARA 8.2 ± 6.4 SARA 12.6 ± 4.8	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	depression 50% (4/8) depression 33% (1/3) depression 13% (2/15) depression 75% (6/8)
(Orsi et al., 2011)	SDS, STAI	SCA1 (n = 6), SCA2 (n = 17), SCA6 (n = 6), SCA8 (n = 4) ²	ICARS 38 ± 14	0	0	NA	NA	NA	72% were depressed, with 47% having a mild disorder
(D'Agata et al., 2011)	SDS, STAI	SCA2 (n = 9), SCA6 (n = 5), SCA7 (n = 2), SCA8 (n = 4) ²	ICARS 46 ± 27	+	0	NA	NA	NA	55% at least mild depression
(Schmitz-Hübsch et al., 2011)	BDI (only in 26 patients), PHQ-9,	SCA1 (n = 117) SCA2 (n = 163) SCA3 (n = 139) SCA6 (n = 107)	SARA 15.6 ± 9.1 SARA 15.8 ± 8.0 SARA 15.1 ± 8.5 SARA 15.2 ± 6.8	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	15.4% depressive according to the clinical impression,

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Title	Methods	Patients	Severity of ataxia	Depression	Anxiety	Apathy	Agitation	Psychosis	Prevalence of NPS	
(Braga-Neto et al., 2012a)	BDI, HAM-A	SCA3 (n = 29)	SARA 13.3 ± 8.4	+	+	NA	NA	NA	17.1% according to PHQ algorithm NA	
(Braga-Neto et al., 2012b)	BDI, HAM-A	SCA3 (n = 38)	SARA 13.2 ± 9.1	+	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	
(Abe et al., 2012)	GDS, apathy score	SCA36 (n = 12)	SARA 21.3 ± 7.4	+	NA	+	NA	NA	NA	
(Fancellu et al., 2013)	HAM-A, HAM-D, SANS, SAPS	SCA1 (n = 20) SCA2 (n = 22)	SARA 12.53 ± 6.4 SARA 14.29 ± 6.56	+	0	+	NA	0	NA NA	
(Wedding et al., 2013)	SCL-90-R	SCA14 (n = 9)	SARA 5.50 ± 3.31 at baseline 8.50 ± 3.62 at follow-up	0	0	NA	0	0	NA	
(Roeske et al., 2013)	BDI	SCA3 (n = 11)	SARA 7.0 ± 5.9 at baseline, 10.2 ± 7.1 at follow-up	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
(Lopes et al., 2013)	BDI, BAI, NPI ⁴	SCA3 (n = 32)	SARA 13.6 ± 6.3	+	+	NA	NA	NA	depression or anxiety in 8 patients (25%)	
(Silva et al., 2015)	DSM-IV	SCA3 (n = 53)	NA	+	0	NA	0	0	49% overall, 45.2% mood disorder, 3.7% anxiety disorder NA	
(Martins et al., 2015)	BDI	SCA1 (n = 12)	NA	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
(Braga-Neto et al., 2016)	DSM-IV, PANSS	SCA3 (n = 112)	SARA 14.89 ± 9.03 in patients with psychotic symptoms, 25 ± 12.72 without psychotic symptoms	NA	NA	NA	NA	+	psychotic symptoms in 4.46%	
(Moriarty et al., 2016)	PHQ-9	SCA1 (n = 2) SCA2 (n = 2) SCA3 (n = 2) SCA6 (n = 4) SCA7 (n = 3)	SARA 10.25 ± 0.35 at baseline, 19.75 ± 6.01 at follow-up SARA 9.5 ± 0.71 at baseline, 14.50 ± 0 at follow-up SARA 20.25 ± 4.6 at baseline, 24.75 ± 4.6 at follow-up SARA 13.13 ± 2.56 at baseline, 17.38 ± 3.54 at follow-up SARA 13.5 ± 4.27 at baseline, 19.5 ± 5.77 at follow-up	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Lo et al., 2016)	PHQ-9	SCA1 (n = 49) SCA2 (n = 64) SCA3 (n = 123) SCA6 (n = 64)	SARA 14.2 ± 8.5 SARA 16.9 ± 7.4 SARA 15.0 ± 8.8 SARA 14.3 ± 7.5	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	depression 24.5% depression 21.9% depression 30.9% depression 21.9%	
(Pedroso et al., 2017)	BDI, HAM-A	SCA2 (n = 33)	SARA 16.80 ± 12.20	+	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	
(Moro et al., 2017)	BDI, HAM-A	SCA3 (n = 28) SCA10 (n = 28)	SARA 15.7 ± 7.3 SARA 9.9 ± 4.5	+	+	NA	NA	NA	NA depression 57%, anxiety 32% 67% overall	
(Choudhury et al., 2018)	NPI	SCA12 (n = 21)	ICARS 41.20 ± 13.81	+	+	+	+	+	depression 57.69%	
(Lin et al., 2018)	BDI	SCA3 (n = 104)	ICARS 27.69 ± 15,76	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	depression 57.69%	
(Turk et al., 2018)	retrospective review of records and live examination and interview of each case	SCA2 (n = 1), SCA3 (n = 3), SCA7 (n = 3), SCA17 (n = 1) ²	NA	+	+	NA	+	+	NA	
(Chirino et al., 2018)	CESD	SCA7 (n = 31)	SARA 14.66 ± 6.26	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
(Yuan et al., 2019)	HAM-A, HAM-D	SCA3 (n = 68)	SARA 11.01 ± 4.97	+	+	NA	NA	NA	depression 48.5% anxiety 42.6%	
(Chen et al., 2019)	BAI, BDI, review of medical records	SCA1 (n = 11) SCA2 (n = 62) SCA3 (n = 102)	NA	0	0	0	0	+	hallucinations in 1 patient depression in 3 patients, hallucinations in 1 patient depression in 4 patients,	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Title	Methods	Patients	Severity of ataxia	Depression	Anxiety	Apathy	Agitation	Psychosis	Prevalence of NPS
									hallucinations in 2 patients
		SCA6 (n = 7)		0	0	0	0	0	
		SCA17 (n = 5)		0	0	0	0	+	hallucinations in 1 patient
(Moro et al., 2020)	BDI	SCA10 (n = 28)	SARA 9 ± 4.3 in patients with fatigue, 10.1 ± 4.7 in patients without fatigue	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Gigante et al., 2020)	BDI	SCA2 (n = 20)	SARA 10.4 ± 4.5	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Martínez-Regueiro et al., 2020)	BDI, HAM-A	SCA36 (n = 30, 11 preataxic, 19 ataxic)	SARA 0.73 ± 1.1 in preataxic group, 16.7 ± 10.1 in ataxic group	+	+	NA	NA	NA	depression 36% (4/11) in preataxic, 63% (11/19) ataxic group, anxiety 18% (2/11) in preataxic, 42% (8/19) ataxic group
(Mastammanavar et al., 2020)	HAM-A, HAM-D,	SCA1 (n = 17)	ICARS 36.0 ± 13.9	+	+	NA	NA	NA	depression 59.52%
		SCA2 (n = 10)	ICARS 39.5 ± 24.4	+	+	NA	NA	NA	
		SCA3 (n = 14)	ICARS 33.7 ± 14.5	+	+	NA	NA	NA	
(Kronemer et al., 2021)	CESD, NPI-Q, interview with patients and informants	SCA1 (n = 1), SCA2 (n = 1), SCA3 (n = 4), SCA6 (n = 8), ARCA1 (n = 1), ILOCA (n = 8), cerebellar ataxia of unknown etiology (n = 16)	SARA 12.83 ± 4.46	+	+	+	0	0	anxiety 65.9%, depression 65.9%, nighttime behaviors 61.0%, irritability 56.1%, disinhibition 51.2%, abnormal appetite 22.0%, agitation 17.1%, apathy 4.9%, hallucinations 2.4%
(Tamaš et al., 2021)	HAM-D, HAM-A	SCA1 (n = 12), SCA2 (n = 6), ILOCA (n = 16)	SARA 15.3 ± 3.8 for SCA, 9.0 ± 3.7 for ILOCA	+	+	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Jacobi et al., 2022)	PHQ-9	SCA1 (n = 173), SCA2 (n = 207), SCA3 (n = 172), SCA6 (n = 125)	SARA 9 for SCA1, 12 for SCA2, 11.5 for SCA3, 13 for SCA3	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Dabla et al., 2022)	BDI	SCA1 (n = 17)	BARS 10.6 ± 4.6	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	depression 23.5% in SCA1, 37.2% in SCA2,
		SCA2 (n = 43)	BARS 12.5 ± 4.5	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	10.3% in SCA12
		SCA12 (n = 29)	BARS 4.1 ± 4.5	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	
(Hengel et al., 2023)	PHQ-9	SCA3 (227 ataxic, 42 pre-ataxic carriers)	SARA 12 in ataxic patients	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	

An important yet still controversial question is whether depression is a result of the neurodegenerative process or rather a consequence of the physical and emotional burden of living with an untreatable progressive illness. Several arguments support the former, but further research is needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms. Moreover, the two theories are not mutually exclusive.

In other neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's disease or Huntington's disease, the commonly comorbid depression is thought to be a part of the neurodegenerative process arising from neuronal loss and disrupted connectivity between basal ganglia, limbic system, and other structures, and imbalances in catecholaminergic, serotonergic and dopaminergic neurotransmitter systems (Aarsland and Kramberger, 2015; Nagy and Schrag, 2019; Paoli et al., 2017). As the neuropathological impairment of the same structures has been described in some cerebellar ataxias, we presume that an analogous mechanism might play a role in the pathophysiology of depression in ataxia patients.

In hereditary ataxia, there is no linear relationship between depressive and motor symptoms, meaning that the most severely disabled individuals are not necessarily the most depressed. (Fancellu et al., 2013; Lo et al., 2016; Moriarty et al., 2016). This phenomenon can be well illustrated in patients with FRDA, who are generally more physically incapacitated while less depressed than patients with SCA, as mentioned above. This evidence suggests that depression is not a mere psychological consequence of motor disability.

Additionally, neuroimaging studies in patients with unipolar or

geriatric depression showed reduced regional cerebral blood flow and cerebellar volume particularly in the vermis, a negative correlation between total cerebellar tissue volume and depression severity, and reduced functional connectivity between the posterior vermis and cingulate cortex, further strengthening the notion of cerebellar involvement in the pathophysiology of depression (Baldaçara et al., 2008; Villanueva, 2012).

A voxel-based morphometry study found a reduction of gray matter volumes in several cortical gyri in depressed FRDA patients as opposed to non-depressed FRDA patients. In addition, BDI scores were inversely correlated with right superior frontal gyrus volume (da Silva et al., 2013a, 2013b). These results support an association between structural changes and depression in FRDA. This can be interpreted as a long-term effect of depression but could also be a consequence of the reverse cerebellar diaschisis due to the aberrant cerebellar connectivity with the frontal cortices, which was demonstrated previously in FRDA patients (Zalesky et al., 2014).

Most studies examining the relation between depression and cognitive impairment found no correlation in this regard in either SCA or FRDA (Gigante et al., 2020; Nieto et al., 2012; Suenaga et al., 2008). In a longitudinal investigation, some patients with SCA even improved in depression ratings whilst deteriorating on cognitive tests (Moriarty et al., 2016). The lack of such connection can be explained by the fact that cognitive impairment and affective symptoms in cerebellar lesions are linked to different pathways – while cognitive deficits are caused by

Table 2
Chronological summary of studies of NPS in FRDA.

Title	Methods	Patients	Severity of ataxia	Depression	Anxiety	Apathy	Agitation	Psychosis	Prevalence of NPS
(White et al., 2000)	HAM-D, SCL-90, semi-structured interview relevant for DSM-IV criteria of major depressive disorder	15	mild to moderate ataxia on upper limbs, moderate to severe on upper limbs	0	0	0	0	0	2/15 patients fulfilled the criteria of a past adjustment disorder with depressed mood
(Mantovan et al., 2006)	MMPI	8	NA	0	0	0	+	0	pathological profiles outside the normal range in half of the FRDA patients
(Corben et al., 2010)	BDI	15	FARS 84.4 ± 25.2	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Corben et al., 2011a)	BDI	13	FARS 84.4 ± 25.2	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Corben et al., 2011b)	BDI	10	FARS 85.0 ± 16.35	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Nieto et al., 2012)	BDI	36	Nobile-Orazio Ataxia Scale 4.31 ± 1.01	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(da Silva et al., 2013a)	BDI	27	FARS 81.3 ± 28.8	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(da Silva et al., 2013b)	BDI	22	FARS 86.4 ± 26.6	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	36.3% fulfilled DSM-IV criteria for major depression
(Nieto et al., 2013)	BDI	36 (29 FRDA, 7 LOFA)	Nobile-Orazio Ataxia Scale 4.34 ± 1.11 in FRDA, 4.14 ± 0.38 in LOFA	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Zalesky et al., 2014)	BDI	13	FARS 86.5 ± 15.7	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Dogan et al., 2016)	HADS	22	SARA 18.61 ± 8.64	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Sayah et al., 2018)	BDI	50	SARA 22.9 ± 9.4	0 ⁵	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Nieto et al., 2018)	BDI	57	SARA 6–37	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	mild depression 19.3%, moderate depression 17.5%, severe depression 3.5%
(Costabile et al., 2018)	DSM-IV, PHQ-9, STAI	20	SARA 18.3 ± 6.1	0	0	NA	NA	NA	personality disorders in three FRDA patients: antisocial, avoidant, and obsessive-compulsive personality disorder
(Reetz et al., 2018)	clinical interview	650	SARA 22 ± 13.3	+	0	NA	NA	NA	depression 14.2%, anxiety 3.1%
(Pérez-Flores et al., 2020)	BDI	62	SARA 22.27 ± 8.64	+	NA	NA	NA	NA	mild depression 23%, moderate depression 23%, severe depression 5%
(Hernández-Torres et al., 2021)	BDI	29	CRS 16.00 ± 6.03 at baseline, 18.38 ± 5.45 at follow-up	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Fichera et al., 2022)	clinical interview	173	14.3 ± 8.6 for disease duration 0–10 years, 23.5 ± 7.4 for disease duration 11–20 years, 30.8 ± 5.1 for disease duration 21–30 years, 32.5 ± 5.3 for disease duration > 30 years	+	+	NA	NA	+	depression or anxiety in 16%, psychotic symptoms in 9%

Notes: + means higher mean scores in patients or higher prevalence of symptoms in patients compared to healthy population, “0” means no significant difference compared to healthy population, “NA” means there are no available data, severity of ataxia is expressed as mean ± standard deviation unless specified otherwise. Case studies were not included in the tables. Relevant case studies: (Chan, 2005; Chen et al., 2012; Ganos et al., 2015; Oruc et al., 2012; Rottnek et al., 2008; Salbenblatt et al., 2000; Singh et al., 2001)

1 An informant assessment scale to evaluate the presence and severity of apathy and irritability according to (Burns et al., 1990)

2 Various subtypes of SCA were evaluated together.

3 The reported prevalence was derived from a graph, exact numbers are not available in the paper.

4 The authors used NPI but do not report the exact results, only the mean score of 11.47 ± 12.26.

5 Borderline BDI score 9.8 ± 8.3, no control group.

Abbreviations: **ARCA1** – autosomal recessive cerebellar ataxia type 1, **BAI** – Beck Anxiety Inventory, **BDI** – Beck Depression Inventory, **CESD** – Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale, **CRS** – Clinical Rating Scale modified from (Appollonio et al., 1993), **DSM-IV** – Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Disorders, **FrSBe** – Frontal Systems Behavior Scale, **GAF** – Global Assessment of Functioning, **GDS** – Geriatric Depression Scale, **HADS** – Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, **HAM-A** – Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale, **HAM-D** – Hamilton Depression Rating Scale, **ILOCA** – Idiopathic Late-Onset Cerebellar Ataxia, **LOFA** – late-onset Friedreich ataxia, **MMPI** – Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory, **NPI** – Neuropsychiatric Inventory, **NPI-Q** – Neuropsychiatric Inventory Questionnaire, **PANSS** – Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale, **PHQ-9** – Patient Health Questionnaire, **SANS** – Scale for Assessment of Negative Symptoms, **SAPS** – Scale for Assessment of Positive

Symptoms, **SCL-90-R** - Symptom Checklist-90-Revised, **SDS** - Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale, **STAI** - State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, **Y-BOCS** - Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale, **YMRS** - Young Mania Rating Scale

Table 3

Summary of the neuropsychiatric symptoms in the most common types of hereditary ataxias.

SCA1	Frequent depression, apathy, and sporadic cases of psychotic symptoms are present. Anxiety does not seem to be a typical feature.
SCA2	Similar neuropsychiatric profile to SCA1, with depression, apathy, and isolated cases of psychosis.
SCA3	The highest prevalence of depression among the SCA subtypes with significantly higher suicidal ideation. Anxiety and apathy are also common. Psychosis is less common, presenting as hallucinations and paranoid delusions.
SCA6	Depression, anxiety, and agitation are common. Isolated reports on apathy and psychosis. Prevalence and severity of neuropsychiatric symptoms are not significantly different from other subtypes despite exclusive cerebellar involvement.
SCA17	Prominent neuropsychiatric symptoms, including depression, anxiety, aggressive behavior, irritability, disinhibition, apathy, and psychosis. Neuropsychiatric symptoms sometimes precede ataxia.
FRDA	Mild depression is present in up to one half of the patients. Irritability, poor impulse control, blunting of affect and inappropriate jocularity were reported. Levels of anxiety do not differ from the healthy population. Cases of psychosis were documented, mainly in later stages of the disease.

Note: As mentioned above, many studies evaluate neuropsychiatric symptoms in SCA as a whole without distinguishing between subtypes, limiting the possibility to draw exact subtype-specific conclusions.

disrupted connectivity between the posterior lobe and association cortices, affective disturbances are associated with lesions in the vermis (Argyropoulos et al., 2020). Another explanation for the discrepancy between cognition and depression in SCA and FRDA might be anosognosia for mood symptoms. Whether endorsed on a rating scale or reported to a clinician, awareness of symptoms is required, and anosognosia would result in false negatives for depression with lower prevalence estimates.

Several studies consistently showed that there was no correlation between depression and the number of CAG repeats in SCA or GAA repeats in FRDA, which represent the underlying genetic mechanisms and their number determines the age of onset and severity of the disease (Cecchin et al., 2006; Nieto et al., 2018; Silva et al., 2015).

Regarding treatment, studies report the use of antidepressants (SSRI or SNRI) in 15–34% of patients with SCA (Lo et al., 2016; Moriarty et al., 2016) and 0–19% of patients with FRDA (Costabile et al., 2018; Sayah et al., 2018), and the use of psychotherapy in 6% of patients with SCA (Lo et al., 2016). The findings suggest that depression is likely undertreated in individuals with hereditary ataxia. The authors of the Clinical Management Guidelines for FRDA recommend the use of antidepressants as well as counseling and lifestyle changes (e.g., exercise, diet, social activities) in management of depression. In the absence of published evidence, the recommendations are based on clinical expertise or evidence from like conditions (Corben et al., 2022). In the future, clinical trials on the safety and efficacy of antidepressant treatment, and efficacy of psychotherapy or other management strategies in ataxia patients should be carried out in order to make more precise, evidence-based recommendations.

3.2. Anxiety

Anxiety is another common neuropsychiatric comorbidity in patients with neurodegenerative disorders (Nagy and Schrag, 2019; Paoli et al., 2017). The cerebellum is connected to the key fear and anxiety-related regions such as the amygdala, midbrain structures, or the prefrontal cortical areas, and findings from functional neuroimaging methods suggest that the cerebellum is involved in the pathophysiology of anxiety disorders, possibly due to its predictive function or other not yet

fully understood mechanisms (Moreno-Rius, 2018).

In SCA, anxiety is more frequent than in the general population and often co-occurs with depression (Pedroso et al., 2017; Yuan et al., 2019). It has been observed in 13–66% of patients with no clear differences between the subtypes, although many of the studies evaluate several SCA subtypes together and may thus overlook the possible distinctions (Kronemer et al., 2021; Leroi et al., 2002). To our knowledge, no studies on anxiety treatment in SCA are currently available.

The few studies examining anxiety in patients with FRDA found no significant difference compared to healthy individuals (Costabile et al., 2018; Dogan et al., 2016). In the case of FRDA patients presenting with symptoms of anxiety, the Clinical Management Guidelines for FRDA recommend the use of anti-anxiety medication and counseling, which is considered more effective than lifestyle changes, based on clinical experience of the authors (Corben et al., 2022).

As in the case of depression, most studies in hereditary ataxia patients use clinical rating scales such as the Hamilton Anxiety Scale (HAMA), the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), or, to a lesser extent, the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI), for the assessment of anxiety symptoms. Some studies also use the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV to diagnose anxiety disorders. However, caution should be taken when interpreting these results. Evaluation by standard questionnaires in hereditary ataxia patients is hindered by similar difficulties as in depression since the somatic symptoms of anxiety (e.g., unsteadiness, tremor) are common symptoms of cerebellar disease and occur in ataxia patients without psychiatric impairment as well.

3.3. Apathy

Apathy is defined as a quantitative reduction of goal-directed activity either in behavioral, cognitive, emotional, or social dimensions in comparison to the patient's previous level of functioning in these areas. Apathy is persistent over time, causes clinically significant functional impairment, and should not be attributable to other disabilities (including motor), substance use, or major environmental changes (Robert et al., 2018). It has been described in a number of neurological and psychiatric diseases, including neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, or Huntington's disease (Le Heron et al., 2019), with new criteria developed specifically for cognitive disorders (Miller et al., 2021).

According to neuroimaging studies performed in non-cerebellar disorders such as Parkinson's or Alzheimer's disease, apathy is associated with disruptions in frontal-subcortical circuitry, most importantly in the anterior cingulate cortex, medial orbitofrontal cortex, and ventral striatum. Of particular interest, studies in patients with Parkinson's disease also found that increased apathy is associated with lower activity and metabolism in the cerebellum and the development of apathy has been reported in patients following an isolated cerebellar stroke (Kos et al., 2016; Le Heron et al., 2018). These findings suggest cerebellar involvement in the pathophysiology of apathy, probably via connections with the frontal cortex and basal ganglia. It has been hypothesized that the cases of cerebellar akinetic mutism observed after acute cerebellar lesions could be considered extreme forms of apathy (Fancellu et al., 2013).

Only a small number of studies examined the presence of apathy in patients with SCA, each using a different approach but agreeing upon the conclusion that apathy is significantly more frequent in patients than in healthy controls (Fancellu et al., 2013; Lasek et al., 2006; Leroi et al., 2002; Zawacki et al., 2002). One exception is a study that used the Neuropsychiatric Inventory Questionnaire (NPI-Q) and did not find a significant difference in apathy scores between patients and healthy individuals (Kronemer et al., 2021). However, this study included a very

heterogeneous group of patients with a large proportion of patients without a genetic confirmation of SCA. In addition, the NPI-Q is an instrument created for evaluating psychopathology in dementia, therefore may not be sensitive enough for patients with SCA. Of note, symptoms of depression and apathy overlap and may be challenging to distinguish.

To our knowledge, no study on apathy in patients with FRDA has been conducted despite the evidence for executive dysfunction, indicating a disruption in frontal-cerebellar circuits in this disorder (Nieto et al., 2012; Sayah et al., 2018).

3.4. Agitation and impulse dyscontrol

Agitation is a common symptom in many neuropsychiatric disorders, although its precise definition and components are not completely agreed upon. According to the International Psychogeriatric Association (IPA), it is broadly defined as a disorder occurring in patients with cognitive impairment, associated with emotional distress, and manifesting with behaviors in the domains of excessive motor activity, verbal aggression, and/or physical aggression. These symptoms must cause excess disability and cannot be the result of another condition or the effects of a substance (Cummings et al., 2015). These criteria have been recently revised and are no longer considered “provisional”, as a testament to their widespread use (Sano et al., 2023). Since cognitive impairment is common in hereditary ataxia as a part of the CCAS, we believe this framework is applicable in this field and we use it here to report on various symptoms observed in ataxia patients.

Several studies, specifically on SCA8 (Torrens et al., 2008), SCA17 (Lasek et al., 2006), and mixed cohorts of SCA1, 2, 3, 6, and 7 (Kronemer et al., 2021; Leroi et al., 2002; Liszewski et al., 2004) observed an increased presence of agitation in ataxia patients (17.1% of patients according to Kronemer et al.). Other symptoms like irritability (56.1%), disinhibition (51.2%), or emotional lability were also found (Kronemer et al., 2021; Leroi et al., 2002). In a study using the NPI-Q, these symptoms were frequently reported by the patients themselves and even more often by their informants (e.g., family and friends) (Kronemer et al., 2021). Personality change is another frequent, although not clearly specified symptom in many SCA patients detected in up to 27% of patients with various subtypes of SCA in one study (Leroi et al., 2002) and in all SCA17 patients in another (Lasek et al., 2006).

Knowledge on agitation and impulse dyscontrol in FRDA is scarce. One study (Mantovan et al., 2006) described increased irritability, poor impulse control, and blunting of affect in half of the patients with FRDA, while another (White et al., 2000) noted the inappropriate jocularity in one third of FRDA patients.

Given the safety issues associated with agitation, more research into this area is required, especially in the framework described by the IPA agitation definition, which allows exploration of different agitation domains (De Mauleon et al., 2021).

3.5. Psychosis

Psychosis is characterized by the presence of hallucinations and/or delusions and as such, is not only a defining component of schizophrenia spectrum disorders but also a common feature of many neurodegenerative diseases (Arciniegas, 2015; Ismail et al., 2022).

Pathophysiology of psychosis in neurodegenerative diseases is likely complex, involving among others the frontal cortex, basal ganglia, or the disruptions of dopaminergic and serotonergic pathways (Jellinger, 2012). However, there is accumulating evidence for cerebellar involvement as well. Newly developed psychotic symptoms were described in children who underwent cerebellar tumor resection, and several neuroimaging and histological studies have demonstrated reduced cerebellar volume and connectivity in patients with schizophrenia leading to promising attempts to use transcranial magnetic stimulation of the cerebellum in the therapy of schizophrenia (Schmahmann et al., 2007; Villanueva, 2012).

Psychotic symptoms, namely visual and auditory hallucinations, and paranoid delusions have been reported in several studies on SCA. One study found psychotic symptoms in 10% of the patients (Leroi et al., 2002), while another reported non-affective psychotic disorders in almost 10% with isolated hallucinations in about 5% (Liszewski et al., 2004). Neither study distinguished between particular subtypes of SCA, but the latter pointed out that psychotic symptoms were present only in the cases with basal ganglia involvement.

Regarding specific subtypes of SCA, psychosis has been described mainly in SCA3 (found in 4.5% in a large cohort of 112 patients) and SCA17, which typically involve basal ganglia (Braga-Neto et al., 2016; Reetz et al., 2010). SCA17 is particularly recognized for its association with psychosis and psychiatric symptoms in general which can even precede ataxic symptoms (Rolfes et al., 2003). Sporadic cases of psychosis have also been reported in SCA1, SCA2, SCA6, SCA7, SCA8, SCA10, and SCA12 (Day et al., 2000; Kronemer et al., 2021; O’Hearn et al., 2001; Trikarnji et al., 2015; Turk et al., 2018).

In FRDA, recent results from a natural history study show an elevated incidence of visual and auditory hallucinations and delusions in patients in very advanced disease stages (up to 18% of patients with disease duration of more than 21 years). Apart from 3 patients suffering from comorbidities possibly predisposing to psychotic symptoms (e.g., bipolar disorder or right internal capsule stroke), all the patients had severe tactile, proprioceptive, visual, and hearing impairment. Several patients retained insight into the unreality of the hallucinations and a diagnosis of Charles Bonnet syndrome (a condition characterized by visual hallucinations occurring in the setting of vision loss) was determined (Fichera et al., 2022; Hamedani and Pelak, 2019). In light of these findings, it has been proposed that some of the psychotic symptoms in FRDA could be explained by deafferentation theory. This theory suggests that hallucinations can arise as a result of low cortical stimulation due to reduced external stimuli and subsequent decrease in threshold for activation in the brain (Fichera et al., 2022). In line with the aforementioned study linking psychotic symptoms with later phases of the disease, a few case reports also presented cases of paranoid delusions and visual, auditory, and somatic hallucinations, usually occurring later in the disease progression (Chan, 2005; Ganos et al., 2015; Oruc et al., 2012; Salbenblatt et al., 2000).

No clinical trials on antipsychotic treatment in ataxia have been conducted, but according to the few documented cases, atypical antipsychotics such as risperidone, olanzapine, quetiapine, or aripiprazole seem to be effective in the treatment of psychotic symptoms both in SCA and in FRDA (Chan, 2005; Chen et al., 2012; Ganos et al., 2015; Oruc et al., 2012; Rottnek et al., 2008; Salbenblatt et al., 2000; Turk et al., 2018; Wexler and Fogel, 2011). The expert authors of Clinical Management Guidelines for FRDA recommend the use of antipsychotic treatment in patients with FRDA, which is favored over counseling, considered less efficacious (Corben et al., 2022). Of note, a single case study also documents a successful treatment of psychotic symptoms by electroconvulsive therapy (ECT) in a FRDA patient diagnosed with bipolar disorder. The link between the psychotic symptoms and FRDA in this case is uncertain, the case study nevertheless suggests that ECT is a safe treatment option in FRDA patients (Singh et al., 2001).

4. Discussion and limitations

NPS are common in hereditary ataxia, particularly in various subtypes of SCA and to a lesser extent in FRDA, where less data is available. While cerebellar impairment probably plays a major role in the development of NPS, degeneration of extracerebellar structures and environmental factors can also contribute.

The relevant literature supports a high prevalence of depression or depressive symptoms in patients with SCA and a significantly higher anxiety level in SCA but not FRDA, compared to the general population. So far, little attention has been paid to other NPS such as apathy, agitation, and psychosis, although several studies also suggest their

presence.

Most of the past studies have used only domain-specific instruments such as various depression and anxiety scales, often self-reported, while omitting other neuropsychiatric domains. Some studies have applied the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Disorders, which is aimed at detecting psychiatric disorders, but may not capture subclinical symptoms and must be administered by a trained mental health professional. Additionally, it is unclear if DSM diagnostic criteria can even be reconciled with the presence of underlying neurodegenerative disease. These methodological differences may also contribute to significant heterogeneity in NPS prevalence estimates.

Considering these facts, we suggest that further research should examine the full range of neuropsychiatric impairment in cerebellar degeneration. We articulate the need for a complex and sensitive, yet easily accessible instrument for evaluating a broad spectrum of NPS in hereditary ataxia patients for future research and clinical practice alike. Caution should be taken with regard to the possible misleading influence of motor symptoms in neuropsychiatric scales.

In recent years, a novel instrument, the Mild Behavioral Impairment Checklist (MBI-C) has been developed, which assesses a broad spectrum of NPS in the early stages of neurodegenerative diseases (Ismail et al., 2017). Its usefulness has been verified both in primary cognitive disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, but also in motor diseases such as Parkinson's disease or motor neuron diseases (Ferraro et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2023; Yoon et al., 2019). No data are yet available about its use in ataxias. However, since the MBI-C does not include items substantially influenced by motor impairment, it may represent a useful and clinically appropriate tool for SCA and FRDA cohorts, which could be evaluated by future studies.

Future research should also integrate instruments measuring the impact of NPS on patients' and caregivers' quality of life.

Information on treatment options is scarce, often only in the form of case reports. Further research, most importantly intervention studies, both pharmacological and non-pharmacological, is needed in order to optimize the care for ataxia patients suffering from NPS.

Our review has several limitations. As the number of papers about NPS in cerebellar ataxias published to date (particularly about other than depressive symptoms) is scarce, we have chosen narrative review with a broad inclusion of the literature. Even though narrative reviews are useful in terms of synthesizing the currently available literature, they do not represent an exhaustive and systematic summary of the topic. Moreover, we acknowledge a possible interpretation bias particularly associated with studies based on retrospective record reviews (Vassar and Matthew, 2013).

In sum, NPS in hereditary ataxia are frequent, with depression and anxiety being the most commonly reported symptoms; however, other symptoms are likely underdiagnosed and therefore undertreated. Following this, we believe there is an urgent need for validated outcome measures that could be used to examine a broader spectrum of NPS in ataxia patients. We advocate integrating a complex NPS examination into natural history studies that are currently ongoing or under preparation. More research attention to this area could improve the quality of life of patients and their families.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

Acknowledgments

Supported by Charles University Grant Agency project GAUK No. 224522 and project National Institute for Neurological Research (Program EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5107) - Funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU. Supported by MH CZ - DRO, Motol University Hospital, Prague, Czech Republic 00064203. The authors of this publication are members of the European Reference Network for

Rare Neurological Diseases.

References

- Aarsland, D., Kramberger, M.G., 2015. Neuropsychiatric symptoms in Parkinson's disease. *J. Park. Dis.* <https://doi.org/10.3233/JPD-150604>.
- Abe, K., Ikeda, Y., Kurata, T., Ohta, Y., Manabe, Y., Okamoto, M., Takamatsu, K., Ohta, T., Takao, Y., Shiro, Y., Shoji, M., Kamiya, T., Kobayashi, H., Koizumi, A., 2012. Cognitive and affective impairments of a novel SCA/MND crossroad mutation Asidan. *Eur. J. Neurol.* 19, 1070–1078. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-1331.2012.03669.x>.
- Appollonio, I.M., Grafman, J., Schwartz, V., Massaquoi, S., Hallett, M., 1993. Memory in patients with cerebellar degeneration, 1536–1536 *Neurology* 43. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.43.8.1536>.
- Arciniegas, D.B., 2015. Psychosis. *CONTINUUM Lifelong Learn. Neurol.* 21, 715–736. <https://doi.org/10.1212/01.CON.0000466662.89908.e7>.
- Argyropoulos, G.P.D., van Dun, K., Adamaszek, M., Leggio, M., Manto, M., Masciullo, M., Molinari, M., Stoodley, C.J., Van Overwalle, F., Ivry, R.B., Schmahmann, J.D., 2020. The cerebellar cognitive affective/schmahmann syndrome: a task force paper. *Cerebellum*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-019-01068-8>.
- Baethge, C., Goldbeck-Wood, S., Mertens, S., 2019. SANRA-a scale for the quality assessment of narrative review articles. *Res. Integr. Peer Rev.* 4, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-019-0064-8>.
- Baldaçara, L., Borgio, J.G.F., Lacerda, A.L.T., de, Jackowski, A.P., 2008. Cerebellum and psychiatric disorders. *Rev. Bras. De. Psiquiatr.* 30, 281–289. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1516-44462008000300016>.
- Braga-Neto, P., Dutra, L.A., Pedrosa, J.L., Felício, A.C., Alessi, H., Santos-Galduroz, R.F., Bertolucci, P.H.F., Castiglioni, M.L.V., Bressan, R.A., de Garrido, G.E.J., Barsottini, O.G.P., Jackowski, A., 2012a. Cognitive deficits in Machado-Joseph disease correlate with hypoperfusion of visual system areas. *Cerebellum* 11, 1037–1044. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-012-0354-x>.
- Braga-Neto, P., Pedrosa, J.L., Alessi, H., Dutra, L.A., Felício, A.C., Minett, T., Weisman, P., Santos-Galduroz, R.F., Bertolucci, P.H.F., Gabbai, A.A., Barsottini, O.G.P., 2012b. Cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome in Machado Joseph disease: core clinical features. *Cerebellum* 11, 549–556. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-011-0318-6>.
- Braga-Neto, P., Pedrosa, J.L., Gadelha, A., Laureano, M.R., de Souza Noto, C., Garrido, G. J., Barsottini, O.G.P., 2016. Psychosis in Machado-Joseph disease: clinical correlates pathophysiological discussion and functional brain imaging. expanding the cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome. *Cerebellum* 15, 483–490. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-015-0716-2>.
- Burns, A., Folstein, S., Brandt, J., Folstein, M., 1990. Clinical assessment of irritability aggression and apathy in Huntington and Alzheimer disease. *J. Nerv. Ment. Dis.* 178, 20–26. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005053-199001000-00004>.
- Cecchin, C.R., Pires, A.P., Rieder, C.R., Monte, T.L., Silveira, L., Carvalho, T., Saraiva-Pereira, M.L., Sequeiros, J., Jardim, L.B., 2006. Depressive symptoms in Machado-Joseph disease (SCA3) patients and their relatives. *Community Genet* 10, 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000096276>.
- Chan, Y.-C., 2005. Aripiprazole treatment for psychosis associated with Friedreich's ataxia. *Gen. Hosp. Psychiatry* 27, 372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.genhosppsych.2005.05.004>.
- Chen, K.H., Lin, C.H., Wu, R.M., 2012. Unusual association of diseases/symptoms: psychotic-affective symptoms and multiple system atrophy expand phenotypes of Spinocerebellar ataxia type 2. *BMJ Case Rep.* 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr.2011.5061>.
- Chen, S.J., Lee, N.C., Chien, Y.H., Hwu, W.L., Lin, C.H., 2019. Heterogeneous nonataxic phenotypes of Spinocerebellar ataxia in a Taiwanese population. *Brain Behav.* 9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/brb3.1414>.
- Chirino, A., Hernandez-Castillo, C.R., Galvez, V., Contreras, A., Diaz, R., Beltran-Parral, L., Fernandez-Ruiz, J., 2018. Motor and cognitive impairments in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 7 and its correlations with cortical volumes. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 48, 3199–3211. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejn.14148>.
- Choudhury, S., Chatterjee, S., Chatterjee, K., Banerjee, R., Humby, J., Mondal, B., Anand, S.S., Shubham, S., Kumar, H., 2018. Clinical characterization of genetically diagnosed cases of Spinocerebellar ataxia type 12 from India. *Mov. Disord. Clin. Pr.* 5, 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mdc3.12551>.
- Cook, A., Giunti, P., 2017. Friedreich's ataxia: clinical features pathogenesis and management. *Br. Med. Bull.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/bmb/ldx034>.
- Corben, L.A., Delatycki, M.B., Bradshaw, J.L., Horne, M.K., Fahey, M.C., Churchyard, A. J., Georgiou-Karistianis, N., 2010. Impairment in motor reprogramming in Friedreich ataxia reflecting possible cerebellar dysfunction. *J. Neurol.* 257, 782–791. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-009-5410-1>.
- Corben, Louise A., Delatycki, M.B., Bradshaw, J.L., Churchyard, A.J., Georgiou-Karistianis, N., 2011a. Utilisation of advance motor information is impaired in Friedreich ataxia. *Cerebellum* 10, 793–803. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-011-0289-7>.
- Corben, L.A., Georgiou-Karistianis, N., Bradshaw, J.L., Hocking, D.R., Churchyard, A.J., Delatycki, M.B., 2011b. The Fitts task reveals impairments in planning and online control of movement in Friedreich ataxia: reduced cerebellar-cortico connectivity. *Neuroscience* 192, 382–390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2011.06.057>.
- Corben, L.A., Collins, V., Milne, S., Farmer, J., Musheno, A., Lynch, D., Subramony, S., Pandolfo, M., Schulz, J.B., Lin, K., Delatycki, M.B., Clinical Management Guidelines Writing Group, 2022. Clinical management guidelines for Friedreich ataxia: best practice in rare diseases. *Orphanet J. Rare Dis.* 17, 415. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-022-02568-3>.

- Costabile, T., Capretti, V., Abate, F., Liguori, A., Paciello, F., Pane, C., De Rosa, A., Peluso, S., De Michele, G., Filla, A., Saccà, F., 2018. Emotion recognition and psychological comorbidity in Friedreich's Ataxia. *Cerebellum* 17, 336–345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-018-0918-5>.
- Cummings, J., Mintzer, J., Brodaty, H., Sano, M., Banerjee, S., Devanand, D.P., Gauthier, S., Howard, R., Lanctôt, K., Lyketsos, C.G., Peskind, E., Porsteinsson, A.P., Reich, E., Sampaio, C., Steffens, D., Wortmann, M., Zhong, K., 2015. Agitation in cognitive disorders: international psychogeriatric association provisional consensus clinical and research definition. *Int Psychogeriatr* 27, 7–17. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610214001963>.
- D'Agata, F., Caroppo, P., Baudino, B., Caglio, M., Croce, M., Bergui, M., Tamietto, M., Mortara, P., Orsi, L., 2011. The recognition of facial emotions in Spinocerebellar ataxia patients. *Cerebellum* 10, 600–610. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-011-0276-z>.
- da Silva, C.B., Chevis, C.F., D'Abreu, A., Lopes-Cendes, I., França, M.C., 2013a. Fatigue is frequent and multifactorial in Friedreich's ataxia. *Park. Relat. Disord.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parkreldis.2013.04.007>.
- Da Silva, C.B., Yasuda, C.L., D'Abreu, A., Cendes, F., Lopes-Cendes, I., França, M.C., 2013b. Neuroanatomical correlates of depression in Friedreich's ataxia: a voxel-based morphometry study. *Cerebellum* 12, 429–436. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-012-0424-0>.
- Dabla, S., Garg, D., Aggarwal, R., Kumar, N., Faruq, M., Rajan, R., Shukla, G., Goyal, V., Pandey, R., Srivastava, A., 2022. Spinocerebellar ataxia 12 patients have better quality of life than Spinocerebellar ataxia 1 and 2. *Ann. Indian Acad. Neurol.* 0, 0. <https://doi.org/10.4103/aian.aian.611.21>.
- Day, J.W., Schut, L.J., Moseley, M.L., Durand, A.C., Ranum, L.P.W., 2000. Spinocerebellar ataxia type 8: clinical features in a large family. *Neurology* 55, 649–657. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.55.5.649>.
- De Mauleon, A., Ismail, Z., Rosenberg, P., Miller, D., Cantet, C., O'Gorman, C., Vellas, B., Lyketsos, C., Soto, M., 2021. Agitation in Alzheimer's disease: novel outcome measures reflecting the International Psychogeriatric Association (IPA) agitation criteria. *Alzheimer's Dement.* 17, 1687–1697. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.12335>.
- Delatycki, M.B., Bidichandani, S.I., 2019. Friedreich ataxia- pathogenesis and implications for therapies. *Neurobiol. Dis.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2019.104606>.
- Dogan, I., Tinnemann, E., Romanzetti, S., Mirzazade, S., Costa, A.S., Werner, C.J., Heim, S., Fedosov, K., Schulz, S., Timmann, D., Giordano, I.A., Klockgether, T., Schulz, J.B., Reetz, K., 2016. Cognition in Friedreich's ataxia: a behavioral and multimodal imaging study. *Ann. Clin. Transl. Neurol.* 3, 572–587. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acn3.315>.
- Fancellu, R., Paridi, D., Tomasello, C., Panzeri, M., Castaldo, A., Genitrini, S., Soliveri, P., Girotti, F., 2013. Longitudinal study of cognitive and psychiatric functions in Spinocerebellar ataxia types 1 and 2. *J. Neurol.* 260, 3134–3143. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-013-7138-1>.
- Ferraro, P.M., Gervino, E., De Maria, E., Meo, G., Ponzano, M., Pardini, M., Signori, A., Schenone, A., Roccatagliata, L., Caponnetto, C., 2023. Mild behavioral impairment as a potential marker of pre-dementia risk states in motor neuron diseases. *Eur. J. Neurol.* 30, 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ene.15570>.
- Fichera, M., Castaldo, A., Mongelli, A., Marchini, G., Gellera, C., Nanetti, L., Mariotti, C., 2022. Comorbidities in Friedreich ataxia: incidence and manifestations from early to advanced disease stages. *Neurol. Sci.* 43, 6831–6838. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-022-06360-w>.
- Ganos, C., Schöttle, D., Zühlke, C., Münchau, A., 2015. Psychosis complicating Friedreich Ataxia. *Mov. Disord. Clin. Pr.* 2, 84–85. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mdc3.12115>.
- Gigante, A.F., Lelli, G., Romano, R., Pellicciari, R., Di Candia, A., Mancino, P.V., Pau, M., Fiore, P., Defazio, G., 2020. The relationships between ataxia and cognition in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 2. *Cerebellum* 19, 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-019-01079-5>.
- Hamedani, A.G., Pelak, V.S., 2019. The Charles bonnet syndrome: a systematic review of diagnostic criteria. *Curr. Treat. Options Neurol.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11940-019-0582-1>.
- Hengel, H., Martus, P., Faber, J., Giunit, P., Garcia-Moreno, H., Solanky, N., Klockgether, T., Reetz, K., van de Warrenburg, B.P., Santana, M.M., Silva, P., Cunha, I., de Almeida, L.P., Timmann, D., Infante, J., de Vries, J., Lima, M., Pires, P., Bushara, K., Jacobi, H., Onyike, C., Schmahmann, J.D., Hübener-Schmid, J., Synofzik, M., Schöls, L., 2023. The frequency of non-motor symptoms in SCA3 and their association with disease severity and lifestyle factors. *J. Neurol.* 270, 944–952. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-022-11441-z>.
- Hernández-Torres, A., Montón, F., Hess Medler, S., De Nóbrega, É., Nieto, A., 2021. Longitudinal study of cognitive functioning in Friedreich's Ataxia. *J. Int. Neuropsychol. Soc.* 27, 343–350. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355617720000958>.
- Hu, S., Patten, S., Charlton, A., Fischer, K., Fick, G., Smith, E.E., Ismail, Z., 2023. Validating the mild behavioral impairment checklist in a cognitive clinic: comparisons with the neuropsychiatric inventory questionnaire. *J. Geriatr. Psychiatry Neurol.* 36, 107–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08919887221093353>.
- Ismail, Z., Agüera-Ortiz, L., Brodaty, H., Cieslak, A., Cummings, J., Fischer, C.E., Gauthier, S., Geda, Y.E., Herrmann, N., Kanji, J., Lanctôt, K.L., Miller, D.S., Morthby, M.E., Onyike, C.U., Rosenberg, P.B., Smith, E.E., Smith, G.S., Sultzer, D.L., Lyketsos, C., 2017. The Mild Behavioral Impairment Checklist (MBI-C): a rating scale for neuropsychiatric symptoms in pre-dementia populations. *J. Alzheimer's Dis.* 56, 929–938. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-160979>.
- Ismail, Z., Gatchel, J., Bateman, D.R., Barcelos-Ferreira, R., Cantillon, M., Jaeger, J., Donovan, N.J., Morthby, M.E., 2018. Affective and emotional dysregulation as pre-dementia risk markers: exploring the mild behavioral impairment symptoms of depression anxiety irritability and euphoria. *Int Psychogeriatr.* 30, 185–196. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610217001880>.
- Ismail, Z., Creese, B., Aarsland, D., Kales, H.C., Lyketsos, C.G., Sweet, R.A., Ballard, C., 2022. Psychosis in Alzheimer disease - mechanisms genetics and therapeutic opportunities. *Nat. Rev. Neurol.* 18, 131–144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41582-021-00597-3>.
- Jacobi, H., Schaprian, T., Beyersmann, J., Tezenas du Montcel, S., Schmid, M., Klockgether, T., 2022. Evolution of disability in Spinocerebellar ataxias type 1 2 3 and 6. *Ann. Clin. Transl. Neurol.* 9, 286–295. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acn3.51515>.
- Jayadev, S., Bird, T.D., 2013. Hereditary ataxias: overview. *Genet. Med.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/gim.2013.28>.
- Jellinger, K.A., 2012. Cerebral correlates of psychotic syndromes in neurodegenerative diseases. *J. Cell Mol. Med.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1582-4934.2011.01311.x>.
- Kawai, Y., Takeda, A., Abe, Y., Washimi, Y., Tanaka, F., Sobue, G., 2004. Cognitive impairments in Machado-Joseph Disease. *Arch. Neurol.* 61, 1757. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archneur.61.11.1757>.
- Klinke, I., Minnerop, M., Schmitz-Hübsch, T., Hendriks, M., Klockgether, T., Wüllner, U., Helmstaedter, C., 2010. Neuropsychological features of patients with Spinocerebellar ataxia (SCA) types 1 2 3 and 6. *Cerebellum* 9, 433–442. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-010-0183-8>.
- Klockgether, T., Mariotti, C., Paulson, H.L., 2019. Spinocerebellar ataxia. *Nat. Rev. Dis. Prim.* 5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41572-019-0074-3>.
- Kos, C., van Tol, M.J., Marsman, J.B.C., Knegtering, H., Aleman, A., 2016. Neural correlates of apathy in patients with neurodegenerative disorders acquired brain injury and psychiatric disorders. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2016.08.012>.
- Kronemer, S.I., Slapik, M.B., Pietrowski, J.R., Margron, M.J., Morgan, O.P., Bakker, C.C., Rosenthal, L.S., Onyike, C.U., Marvel, C.L., 2021. Neuropsychiatric symptoms as a reliable phenomenology of Cerebellar Ataxia. *Cerebellum* 20, 141–150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-020-01195-7>.
- Lasek, K., Lencer, R., Gaser, C., Hagenah, J., Walter, U., Wolters, A., Kock, N., Steinlechner, S., Nagel, M., Zühlke, C., Nitschke, M.F., Brockmann, K., Klein, C., Rolfs, A., Binkofski, F., 2006. Morphological basis for the spectrum of clinical deficits in Spinocerebellar ataxia 17 (SCA17). *Brain* 129, 2341–2352. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awl148>.
- Le Heron, C., Apps, M.A.J., Husain, M., 2018. The anatomy of apathy: a neurocognitive framework for amotivated behaviour. *Neuropsychologia* 118, 54–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2017.07.003>.
- Le Heron, C., Holroyd, C.B., Salamone, J., Husain, M., 2019. Brain mechanisms underlying apathy. *J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiatry* 90, 302–312. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jnnp-2018-318265>.
- Leroi, I., O'Hearn, E., Marsh, L., Lyketsos, C.G., Rosenblatt, A., Ross, C.A., Brandt, J., Margolis, R.L., 2002. Psychopathology in patients with degenerative cerebellar diseases: a comparison to Huntington's Disease. *Am. J. Psychiatry* 159, 1306–1314. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.app.159.8.1306>.
- Lin, M.T., Yang, J.S., Chen, P.P., Qian, M.Z., Lin, H.X., Chen, X.P., Shang, X.J., Wang, D.N., Chen, Y.C., Jiang, B., Chen, Y.J., Chen, W.J., Wang, N., Gan, S.R., 2018. Bidirectional connections between depression and Ataxia Severity in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 3 patients. *Eur. Neurol.* 79, 266–271. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000489398>.
- Liszewski, C.M., Elizabeth, B.O., Leroi, I., Gourley, L., Christopher Ross, M.A., Margolis, R.L., 2004. Cognitive impairment and psychiatric symptoms in 133 patients with diseases associated with cerebellar degeneration. *J. Neuropsychiatry Clin. Neurosci.* <https://doi.org/10.1176/jnp.16.1.109>.
- Lo, R.Y., Figueroa, K.P., Pulst, S.M., Perlman, S., Wilmut, G., Gomez, C., Schmahmann, J., Paulson, H., Shakkottai, V.G., Ying, S., Zesiewicz, T., Bushara, K., Geschwind, M., Xia, G., Yu, J.T., Lee, L.E., Ashizawa, T., Subramony, S.H., Kuo, S.H., 2016. Depression and clinical progression in Spinocerebellar ataxias. *Park. Relat. Disord.* 22, 87–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parkreldis.2015.11.021>.
- Lopes, T.M., D'Abreu, A., Junior, M.C.F., Yasuda, C.L., Betting, L.E., Samara, A.B., Castellano, G., Somazzi, J.C., Balthazar, M.L.F., Lopes-Cendes, I., Cendes, F., 2013. Widespread neuronal damage and cognitive dysfunction in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 3. *J. Neurol.* 260, 2370–2379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-013-6998-8>.
- Malhi, G.S., Mann, J.J., 2018. Depression. *Lancet.* [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31948-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31948-2).
- Mantovan, M.C., Martinuzzi, A., Squaranti, F., Bolla, A., Silvestri, I., Liessi, G., Macchi, C., Ruzza, G., Trevisan, C.P., Angelini, C., 2006. Exploring mental status in Friedreich's ataxia: a combined neuropsychological behavioral and neuroimaging study. *Eur. J. Neurol.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-1331.2006.01363.x>.
- Martínez-Regueiro, R., Arias, M., Cruz, R., Quintáns, B., Labella-Caballero, T., Pardo, M., Pardo, J., García-Murias, M., Carracedo, A., Sobrido, M.J., Fernández-Prieto, M., 2020. Cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome in Costa da Morte Ataxia (SCA36). *Cerebellum* 19, 501–509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-020-01110-0>.
- Martins, C.R., Martínez, A.R.M., D'Abreu, A., Lopes-Cendes, I., França, M.C., 2015. Fatigue is frequent and severe in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 1. *Park. Relat. Disord.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parkreldis.2015.04.015>.
- Mastammanavar, V.S., Kambale, N., Yadav, R., Netravathi, M., Jain, S., Kumar, K., Pal, P. K., 2020. Non-motor symptoms in patients with autosomal dominant Spinocerebellar ataxia. *Acta Neurol. Scand.* 142, 368–376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ane.13318>.
- McMurtry, A.M., Clark, D.G., Flood, M.K., Susan Perlman, P., Mendez, M.F., 2006. Depressive and memory symptoms as presenting features of Spinocerebellar ataxia. *J. Neuropsychiatry Clin. Neurosci.* <https://doi.org/10.1176/jnp.2006.18.3.420>.
- Miller, D.S., Robert, P., Ereshefsky, L., Adler, L., Bateman, D., Cummings, J., DeKosky, S. T., Fischer, C.E., Husain, M., Ismail, Z., Jaeger, J., Lerner, A.J., Li, A., Lyketsos, C.G., Manera, V., Mintzer, J., Moebius, H.J., Morthby, M., Meulien, D., Pollentier, S., Porsteinsson, A., Rasmussen, J., Rosenberg, P.B., Ruthirakuhlan, M.T., Sano, M., Zuccherro Sarracini, C., Lanctôt, K.L., 2021. Diagnostic criteria for apathy in

- neurocognitive disorders. *Alzheimer's Dement.* 17, 1892–1904. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.12358>.
- Moreno-Rius, J., 2018. The cerebellum in fear and anxiety-related disorders. *Prog. Neuropharmacol. Biol. Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2018.04.002>.
- Moriarty, A., Cook, A., Hunt, H., Adams, M.E., Cipolotti, L., Giunti, P., 2016. A longitudinal investigation into cognition and disease progression in Spinocerebellar ataxia types 1 2 3 6 and 7. *Orphanet J. Rare Dis.* 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-016-0447-6>.
- Moro, A., Munhoz, R.P., Moscovich, M., Arruda, W.O., Raskin, S., Silveira-Moriyama, L., Ashizawa, T., Teive, H.A.G., 2017. Nonmotor symptoms in patients with Spinocerebellar ataxia type 10. *Cerebellum* 16, 938–944. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-017-0869-2>.
- Moro, A., Munhoz, R.P., Camargo, C.H., Moscovich, M., Farah, M., Teive, H.A.G., 2020. Is fatigue an important finding in patients with Spinocerebellar ataxia type 10 (SCA10). *J. Clin. Neurosci.* 71, 150–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2019.08.097>.
- Nagy, A., Schrag, A., 2019. Neuropsychiatric aspects of Parkinson's disease. *J. Neural Transm.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-019-02019-7>.
- Nieto, A., Correia, R., de Nóbrega, E., Montón, F., Hess, S., Barroso, J., 2012. Cognition in Friedreich Ataxia. *Cerebellum* 11, 834–844. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-012-0363-9>.
- Nieto, A., Correia, R., de Nóbrega, E., Montón, F., Barroso, J., 2013. Cognition in late-onset Friedreich Ataxia. *Cerebellum* 12, 504–512. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-013-0457-z>.
- Nieto, A., Hernández-Torres, A., Pérez-Flores, J., Montón, F., 2018. Depressive symptoms in Friedreich ataxia. *Int. J. Clin. Health Psychol.* 18, 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijchp.2017.11.004>.
- O'Hearn, E., Holmes, S.E., Calvert, P.C., Ross, C.A., Margolis, R.L., 2001. SCA-12: tremor with cerebellar and cortical atrophy is associated with a CAG repeat expansion. *Neurology* 56, 299–303. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.56.3.299>.
- Orsi, L., D'Agata, F., Caroppo, P., Franco, A., Caglio, M.M., Avidano, F., Manzoni, C., Mortara, P., 2011. Neuropsychological picture of 33 Spinocerebellar ataxia cases. *J. Clin. Exp. Neuropsychol.* 33, 315–325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803395.2010.518139>.
- Oruc, S., Gulseren, G., Kusbeci, O.Y., Yaman, M., Gecici, O., 2012. Quetiapine treatment for psychosis in Friedreich's Ataxia. *Klin. Psikofarmakol. Bülteni-Bull. Clin. Psychopharmacol.* 22, 357–358. <https://doi.org/10.5455/bcp.20120729093746>.
- Paoli, R., Botturi, A., Ciammola, A., Silani, V., Prunas, C., Lucchiarri, C., Zugno, E., Caletti, E., 2017. Neuropsychiatric burden in Huntington's Disease. *Brain Sci.* 7, 67. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci7060067>.
- Pedroso, J.L., Braga-Neto, P., Escorico-Bezerra, M.L., Abrahão, A., de Albuquerque, M.V.C., Filho, F.M.R., de Souza, P.V.S., de Rezende Pinto, W.B.V., Borges, F.R.P., Saraiva-Pereira, M.L., Jardim, L.B., Barsottini, O.G.P., 2017. Non-motor and extracerebellar features in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 2. *Cerebellum* 16, 34–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-016-0761-5>.
- Pérez-Flores, J., Hernández-Torres, A., Montón, F., Nieto, A., 2020. Health-related quality of life and depressive symptoms in Friedreich ataxia. *Qual. Life Res.* 29, 413–420. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-019-02311-9>.
- Reetz, K., Lencer, R., Hagenah, J.M., Gaser, C., Tadic, V., Walter, U., Wolters, A., Steinlechner, S., Zühlke, C., Brockmann, K., Klein, C., Rolfs, A., Binkowski, F., 2010. Structural changes associated with progression of motor deficits in Spinocerebellar ataxia 17. *Cerebellum* 9, 210–217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-009-0150-4>.
- Reetz, K., Dogan, I., Hohenfeld, C., Didszun, C., Giunti, P., Mariotti, C., Durr, A., Boesch, S., Klopstock, T., Rodríguez de Rivera Garrido, F.J., Schöls, L., Giordano, I., Bürk, K., Pandolfo, M., Schulz, J.B., 2018. Nonataxia symptoms in Friedreich Ataxia: report from the registry of the European Friedreich's Ataxia Consortium for Translational Studies (EFACTS). *Neurology* 91, e917–e930. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.00000000000006121>.
- Reiff, J., Schmidt, N., Riebe, B., Breternitz, R., Aldenhoff, J., Deuschl, G., Witt, K., 2011. Subthreshold depression in Parkinson's disease. *Mov. Disord.* 26, 1741–1744. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.23699>.
- Robert, P., Lancôt, K.L., Agüera-Ortiz, L., Aalten, P., Bremond, F., Defrancesco, M., Hanon, C., David, R., Dubois, B., Dujardin, K., Husain, M., König, A., Levy, R., Mantua, V., Meulien, D., Miller, D., Moebius, H.J., Rasmussen, J., Robert, G., Ruthirakuhan, M., Stella, F., Yesavage, J., Zeghari, R., Manera, V., 2018. Is it time to revise the diagnostic criteria for apathy in brain disorders? the 2018 international consensus group. *Eur. Psychiatry* 54, 71–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2018.07.008>.
- Roeske, S., Filla, I., Heim, S., Amunts, K., Helmstaedter, C., Wüllner, U., Wagner, M., Klockgether, T., Minnerop, M., 2013. Progressive cognitive dysfunction in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 3. *Mov. Disord.* 28, 1435–1438. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.25512>.
- Rolfs, A., Koepfen, A.H., Bauer, I., Bauer, P., Buhlmann, S., Topka, H., Schöls, L., Riess, O., 2003. Clinical features and neuropathology of autosomal dominant Spinocerebellar ataxia (SCA17). *Ann. Neurol.* 54, 367–375. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.10676>.
- Rottnek, M., Riggio, S., Byne, W., Sano, M., Margolis, R.L., Walker, R.H., 2008. Schizophrenia in a patient with Spinocerebellar ataxia 2: coincidence of two disorders or a neurodegenerative disease presenting with psychosis. *Am. J. Psychiatry* 964–967. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2008.08020285>.
- Ruano, L., Melo, C., Silva, M.C., Coutinho, P., 2014. The global epidemiology of hereditary ataxia and spastic paraplegia: a systematic review of prevalence studies. *Neuroepidemiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000358801>.
- Salbenblatt, M.J., Buzan, R.D., Dubovsky, S.L., 2000. Risperidone treatment for psychosis in end-stage Friedreich's ataxia. *Am. J. Psychiatry* 157, 303. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.157.2.303>.
- Sano, M., Cummings, J., Auer, S., Bergh, S., Fischer, C.E., Gerritsen, D., Grossberg, G., Ismail, Z., Lancôt, K., Lapid, M.I., Mintzer, J., Palm, R., Rosenberg, P.B., Splaine, M., Zhong, K., Zhu, C.W., 2023. Agitation in cognitive disorders: progress in the International Psychogeriatric Association consensus clinical and research definition. *Int. Psychogeriatr.* 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610222001041>.
- Saute, J.A.M., Da Silva, A.C.F., Donis, K.C., Vedolin, L., Saraiva-Pereira, M.L., Jardim, L. B., 2010. Depressive mood is associated with ataxic and non-ataxic neurological dysfunction in SCA3 patients. *Cerebellum*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-010-0205-6>.
- Sayah, S., Rotgé, J.Y., Francisque, H., Gargiulo, M., Czernecki, V., Justo, D., Lahlou-Laforet, K., Hahn, V., Pandolfo, M., Pelissolo, A., Fossati, P., Durr, A., 2018. Personality and neuropsychological profiles in Friedreich Ataxia. *Cerebellum* 17, 204–212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-017-0890-5>.
- Schmahmann, J., 1998a. The cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome. *Brain* 121, 561–579. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/121.4.561>.
- Schmahmann, J.D., 1998b. Dysmetria of thought: clinical consequences of cerebellar dysfunction on cognition and affect. *Trends Cogn. Sci.* 2, 362–371. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613\(98\)01218-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613(98)01218-2).
- Schmahmann, J.D., Weilburg, J.B., Sherman, J.C., 2007. The neuropsychiatry of the cerebellum - Insights from the clinic. *Cerebellum*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14734220701490995>.
- Schmahmann, J.D., Pierce, S., MacMore, J., L'Italien, G.J., 2021. Development and Validation of a patient-reported outcome measure of ataxia. *Mov. Disord.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.28670>.
- Schmitz-Hübisch, T., Coudert, M., Giunti, P., Globas, C., Baliko, L., Fancellu, R., Mariotti, C., Filla, A., Rakowicz, M., Charles, P., Ribai, P., Szymanski, S., Infante, J., Van De Warrenburg, B.P.C., Dürr, A., Timmann, D., Boesch, S., Rola, R., Depondt, C., Schöls, L., Zdzienicka, E., Kang, J.S., Ratzka, S., Kremer, B., Schulz, J.B., Klopstock, T., Melegh, B., Du Montcel, S.T., Klockgether, T., 2010. Self-rated health status in Spinocerebellar ataxia - results from a European multicenter study. *Mov. Disord.* 25, 587–595. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.22740>.
- Schmitz-Hübisch, T., Coudert, M., Tezenas du Montcel, S., Giunti, P., Labrum, R., Dürr, A., Ribai, P., Charles, P., Linnemann, C., Schöls, L., Rakowicz, M., Rola, R., Zdzienicka, E., Fancellu, R., Mariotti, C., Baliko, L., Melegh, B., Filla, A., Salvatore, E., van de Warrenburg, B.P.C., Szymanski, S., Infante, J., Timmann, D., Boesch, S., Depondt, C., Kang, J.S., Schulz, J.B., Klopstock, T., Losznier, N., Löwe, B., Frick, C., Rottländer, D., Schlaepfer, T.E., Klockgether, T., 2011. Depression comorbidity in Spinocerebellar ataxia. *Mov. Disord.* 26, 870–876. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.23698>.
- Silva, U.C.A., Marques, W., Lourenço, C.M., Hallak, J.E.C., Osório, F.L., 2015. Psychiatric disorders Spinocerebellar ataxia type 3 and CAG expansion. *J. Neurol.* 262, 1777–1779. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-015-7807-3>.
- Singh, G., Binstadt, A., Black, F., Corr, P., Rummans, T.A., 2001. *Electroconvulsive Therapy and Friedreich's Ataxia*. The J. ECT.
- Suenaga, M., Kawai, Y., Watanabe, H., Atsuta, N., Ito, M., Tanaka, F., Katsuno, M., Fukutsu, H., Naganawa, S., Sobue, G., 2008. Cognitive impairment in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 6. *J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiatry* 79, 496–499. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jnnp.2007.119883>.
- Tamaš, O., Kostić, M., Kačar, A., Stefanova, E., Đokić, B.S., Stanisavljević, D., Milovanović, A., Dorđević, M., Glumbić, N., Dragasević-Mišković, N., 2021. Social cognition in patients with cerebellar neurodegenerative disorders. *Front. Syst. Neurosci.* 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsys.2021.664223>.
- Torrens, L., Burns, E., Stone, J., Graham, C., Wright, H., Summers, D., Sellar, R., Porteous, M., Warner, J., Zeman, A., 2008. Spinocerebellar ataxia type 8 in Scotland: frequency neurological neuropsychological and neuropsychiatric findings. *Acta Neurol. Scand.* 117, 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0404.2007.00904.x>.
- Trikamji, B., Singh, P., Mishra, S., 2015. Spinocerebellar ataxia-10 with paranoid schizophrenia. *Ann. Indian Acad. Neurol.* 18, 93–95. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-2327.144285>.
- Turk, K.W., Flanagan, M.E., Josephson, S., Keene, C.D., Jayadev, S., Bird, T.D., 2018. Psychosis in Spinocerebellar ataxias: a Case Series and Study of Tyrosine Hydroxylase in Substantia Nigra. *Cerebellum* 17, 143–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-017-0882-5>.
- Vassar, M., Matthew, H., 2013. The retrospective chart review: important methodological considerations. *J. Educ. Eval. Health Prof.* 10, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3352/jeehp.2013.10.12>.
- Villanueva, R., 2012. The cerebellum and neuropsychiatric disorders. *Psychiatry Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2012.02.023>.
- Wedding, I.M., Koht, J., Dietrichs, E., Landro, N.I., Tallaksen, C.M., 2013. Cognition is only minimally impaired in Spinocerebellar ataxia type 14 (SCA14): a neuropsychological study of ten Norwegian subjects compared to intrafamilial controls and population norm.
- Wexler, E., Fogel, B.L., 2011. New-onset psychosis in a patient with Spinocerebellar ataxia type 10. *Am. J. Psychiatry* 168, 1339–1340. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2011.11050737>.
- White, M., Lalonde, R., Botez-Marquard, T., 2000. Neuropsychologic and neuropsychiatric characteristics of patients with Friedreich's ataxia. *Acta Neurol. Scand.* 102, 222–226. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0404.2000.102004222.x>.
- Yoon, E.J., Ismail, Z., Hanganu, A., Kibreab, M., Hammer, T., Cheetham, J., Kathol, I., Sarna, J.R., Martino, D., Furtado, S., Monchi, O., 2019. Mild behavioral impairment is linked to worse cognition and brain atrophy in Parkinson disease. *Neurology* 93, e766–e777. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.0000000000007968>.

- Yuan, X., Ou, R., Hou, Y., Chen, X., Cao, B., Hu, X., Shang, H., 2019. Extra-cerebellar signs and nonmotor features in Chinese patients with spinocerebellar ataxia type 3. *Front. Neurol.* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2019.00110>.
- Zalesky, A., Akhlaghi, H., Corben, L.A., Bradshaw, J.L., Delatycki, M.B., Storey, E., Georgiou-Karistianis, N., Egan, G.F., 2014. Cerebello-cerebral connectivity deficits in Friedreich ataxia. *Brain Struct. Funct.* 219, 969–981. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00429-013-0547-1>.
- Zawacki, T.M., Grace, J., Friedman, J.H., Sudarsky, L., 2002. Executive and emotional dysfunction in Machado-Joseph disease. *Mov. Disord.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.10033>.